

A Comparative Study of Performances Between the Sliding Modes and the Trust Control Strategies for an Articulated Robotic Arm Position Control

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Abstract— Two robust control techniques are presented and applied to a SCARA robotic arm in order to analyze the performances in terms of precision and quality of the control signals. The first controller is the very well known sliding modes (SM) based controller. It has been applied successfully so far in various applications. Its main drawback is certainly the Shattering phenomenon and the high energy of the control signals deployed to overcome the modelling and measurement errors. The second controller is a brand new controller called the trust control. The trust controller is based on the Dempster-Shafer belief theory concepts. Its robustness with regard to the measurement and modelling errors is mainly due to the use of the trust allocated to the information sources (measurements and estimations) rather than the direct use of the data itself (possibly incorrect) in the control strategy computation. Simulations have been carried out, they underline the robustness of the trust controller and its higher precision and less energetic control signals, with comparison to the SM controller.

Index Term— Articulated robotic arm, Robust control, Sliding modes, Belief theory, Trust control.

I. INTRODUCTION

ROBOTIC arms modeling is still an ongoing research field. Robots modelling is very well known for the lack of precision due to the several approximations and dynamics simplifications that aim to simplify the models, therefore the

control laws. Since the control signals computation relies mostly on the mathematical model of the system, the robustness of the controller seems to be the key of the success of the control task. Most of the robust control techniques found in the literature focus on the estimation of the nonlinearities and errors [1], [2], [3], [4]. These techniques rely mostly on the robot models and the estimation of its parameters, which leaves the problem of omitted dynamics unsolved. Such methods also imply a good knowledge of the model structure that has to be chosen, which is hardly achieved in real life.

The Sliding Modes technique and its variants remains the most promising technique today [5], [6] in terms of managing the modeling and measurement errors. The shattering phenomenon remains though a severe inconvenient even with the recent efforts and variants of this technique [7].

The belief theory has proved its efficiency in several problems solving, such as mobile robots localization, parameters estimation, navigation and medical diagnosis [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13], [14]. The robustness of the Belief theory based techniques has been proven in [11], [12] for localization and state estimation problems and in [15] to control and reduce tumor growth under modelling and measurement uncertainties. This paper attempts to use a new robust controller based on the belief theory in order to achieve trajectory tracking for a robotic arm with precision and robustness to modelling and measurement errors, while improving the outputs and control signals quality compared

to the ones obtained using the Sliding Modes controller in similar operating conditions. This novel controller is called the trust control. It mainly relies on the trust allocated to the measurement data considered as a first source of information and the model data considered as a second source of information, with balanced degrees of trust allocated to each source of information.

The second section of this manuscript introduces the tools and materials, including the robot arm and its several mathematical models, together with the forward and inverse kinematics, the SCARA manipulator and its joint variables [16], the forward and inverse differential motion and the dynamical equations. This same section presents the generation of trajectories as references for the joint variables of the robot arm. It also presents the control methodology including the Sliding Modes and trust controllers that will be used in a comparative analysis of performances. The third section presents the comparative study between the two robust controllers' results. The performances in terms of precision and control energies demonstrate better results for the trust control compared to the ones obtained with the sliding modes technique.

II. TOOLS AND MATERIALS

A. Articulated robotic arm modelling

Multiple approaches to model a robotic arm kinematics, motion and dynamics have been widely covered in the literature. The most common modeling approaches aim to express the position and orientation as well as the speeds and accelerations of the robotic arm in the base frame. The homogenous matrices based on Euler angles, the Denavit-Hartenberg (D-H) formulation and algorithm [17], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22] as well as the quaternions and dual quaternions are the most popular methods to model a rigid robot arm's position and orientation [23], [24], [25], [26], [27], [28], [29], [30], [31], [32], [33], [34], [35], [36]. The Jacobian, inverse, pseudo-inverse and generalized-inverse matrices are used to model the forward and inverse differential motion. The Euler-Lagrange formalism is used to express the accelerations or the dynamic model.

In the following, we present a recall on the D-H formulation and algorithm that will result in a matrix that gathers both information on the orientation and the position of the en-effector of a robotic arm.

The Denavit-Hartenberg formulation

Considering a n joints articulated robotic arm, the D-H formulation allows the determination of the frame associated to the k^{th} joint as well as the geometric parameters of the robot associated to the k^{th} link and the k^{th} joint, namely the link length a_k , the joint angle θ_k , the link offset d_k and the link twist α_k [17], [18], [37], [38].

The D-H formalism can be applied following the algorithm description:

1. Label the joint axes by z_0, z_1, \dots, z_{n-1} ;
2. Set the origin O_0 on z_0 and use the right hand rule to choose x_0 and y_0 to form the base frame (O_0, x_0, y_0, z_0) ;
3. Set the origin O_k at the intersection of z_k and z_{k-1} . If z_k and z_{k-1} don't intersect, locate O_k in a convenient position on z_k ;
4. Establish the common normal to z_{k-1} and z_k as x_k ;
5. Use the right hand rule to form the frame (O_k, x_k, y_k, z_k) ;
6. Set the end-effector frame (O_n, x_n, y_n, z_n) in a suitable configuration following the right hand rule;
7. Determine the link's parameters:
 - a_k The distance between O_k and the intersection of x_k and z_{k-1} , measured along x_k ;
 - α_k the angle between z_{k-1} and z_k about x_k
 - d_k The distance between O_{k-1} and the intersection of x_k and z_{k-1} , measured along z_{k-1} . If the joint is prismatic, then d_k is the joint variable q_k ;
 - θ_k the angle between x_{k-1} and x_k about z_{k-1} . If the joint is revolute, then θ_k is the joint variable q_k ;
8. Compute the transformation matrix T_{k-1}^k as the following

$$T_{k-1}^k = \begin{pmatrix} C\theta_i & -S\theta_i C\alpha_i & S\theta_i S\alpha_i & a_i C\theta_i \\ S\theta_i & C\theta_i C\alpha_i & -C\theta_i S\alpha_i & a_i S\theta_i \\ 0 & S\theta_i & C\alpha_i & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Where $C\theta_i$, $S\theta_i$, $C\alpha_i$ and $S\alpha_i$ refer respectively to $\cos(\theta_i)$, $\sin(\theta_i)$, $\cos(\alpha_i)$ and $\sin(\alpha_i)$.

9. Compute the matrix $T_0^n = \prod_{i=1}^n T_{i-1}^i$ in order to obtain the position and orientation of the robot expressed in the base frame.

Figure 1 and Table I illustrate a SCARA robotic arm joint frames and parameters according to the D-H formulation.

Fig. 1. Application of the D-H formulation for a SCARA robot arm.

TABLE I

THE PARAMETERS OF THE SCARA ROBOTIC ARM ACCORDING TO THE D-H FORMULATION

Link	a_k	α_k	d_k	θ_k
1	a_1	π	d_1	q_1
2	a_2	0	0	q_2
3	0	0	q_3	

The Forward and Inverse kinematics

The forward kinematics describes the robotic arm position and orientation depending on the joints variables q , whereas the inverse kinematics computes the joints variables given a position and orientation for the end effector of the robotic arm.

Using the D-H formulation, the matrix T_0^n depends on the joints variables of the robot and gives the forward kinematics model (2).

$$T_0^n = \prod_1^n T_{k-1}^k = \begin{pmatrix} R & P \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

P and R respectively express the position and the orientation of the end effector.

The inverse kinematics is obtained by solving equation (2) in terms of the joint variables.

For the example of the SCARA robotic arm given in Figure 1, the forward and inverse kinematics related to the position of the robot are presented, respectively, in (3) and (4).

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} P_x \\ P_y \\ P_z \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 C_1 + a_2 C_{1-2} \\ a_1 S_1 + a_2 S_{1-2} \\ -q_3 + d_1 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3)$$

C_{1-2} and S_{1-2} denote, respectively, $\cos(q_1 - q_2)$ and $\sin(q_1 - q_2)$.

$$q = \begin{pmatrix} q_1 \\ q_2 \\ q_3 \end{pmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$= \begin{pmatrix} \text{atan2}(a_2 S_2 P_x + (a_1 + a_2 C_2) P_y, (a_1 + a_2 C_2) P_x - a_2 S_2 P_y) \\ \pm \arccos\left(\frac{P_x^2 + P_y^2 - a_1^2 - a_2^2}{2a_1 a_2}\right) \\ d - P_z \end{pmatrix}$$

The Forward and inverse differential motion

The forward differential motion describes the robotic arm speeds in the base frame depending on the joint speeds \dot{q} , whereas the inverse differential motion gives the joint speeds knowing the end effector's speed expressed in the base frame.

The Jacobian matrix V , the pseudo-inverse V^+ and the generalized inverse V^g are the tools used to compute the forward and inverse differential motion models.

For a position control problem, for instance, the forward and inverse differential motion models are expressed in (5) and (6), respectively.

$$\dot{P} = V\dot{q} \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{q} = V^{-1}\dot{P} \quad (6)$$

If V can't be inverted, then the pseudo-inverse V^+ or the generalized inverse V^g should be used instead [39], [40] as presented in (7) and (8).

$$V^+ = (V^T V)^{-1} V \quad (7)$$

$$V^g = L \Sigma^{-1} r^T \quad (8)$$

Σ is a diagonal matrix that contains the eigenvalues of V .

L and r are the left and right eigenvectors of the matrix V .

For the SCARA robotic arm manipulator illustrated in Figure 1, the differential kinematics equations are presented in (9).

$$\dot{P} = \begin{pmatrix} -(a_1 S_1 + a_2 S_{1-2}) & a_2 S_{1-2} & 0 \\ a_1 C_1 + a_2 C_{1-2} & -a_2 C_{1-2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \dot{q} \quad (9)$$

The Dynamical model

The dynamical model expresses the forces and torques of the end effector function of the joints accelerations \ddot{q} . This model is the key part of the control process as it is usually used to compute and implement the control signals. It also is the hardest model to determine, as it involves many approximations and simplifications of dynamics due to ignorance or for the sake of simplicity. These approximations and simplifications result irrevocably in imprecise models, thus introduce modeling errors.

The Euler-Lagrange formulation (10) is so far the most used approach to compute the dynamical model of a robotic arm.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \frac{\partial}{\partial \dot{q}_k} L(q, \dot{q}) - \frac{\partial}{\partial q_k} L(q, \dot{q}) = \tau_k, \quad k = 1, \dots, n \quad (10)$$

$L(q, \dot{q}) = T(q, \dot{q}) - U(q)$ is the Lagrangian

$T(q, \dot{q})$ and $U(q)$ are the kinetic and potential energies, respectively.

After computations and simplifications, equation (10) can be usually written as (11). This last formulation highlights the inertial matrix $M(q)$, the Coriolis forces vector $C(q, \dot{q})$, the viscous friction vector $B(\dot{q})$ and the gravity forces vector G .

$$M(q)\ddot{q} + C(q, \dot{q}) + B(\dot{q}) + G = \tau \quad (11)$$

The matrices that intervene in the computation of the dynamical model of the SCARA robotic arm presented in Figure 1 are given in (12), (13), (14) and (15) [16].

$$M(q) = \begin{pmatrix} M_{11}(q) & M_{12}(q) & M_{13}(q) \\ M_{21}(q) & M_{22}(q) & M_{23}(q) \\ M_{31}(q) & M_{32}(q) & M_{33}(q) \end{pmatrix} \quad (12)$$

$$M_{11}(q) = \left(\frac{m_1}{3} + m_2 + m_3\right) a_1^2 + (m_2 + 2m_3) a_1 a_2 C_2 + \left(\frac{m_2}{3} + m_3\right) a_2^2$$

$$M_{12}(q) = -\left(\frac{m_2}{2} + m_3\right) a_1 a_2 C_2 - \left(\frac{m_2}{3} + m_3\right) a_2^2$$

$$M_{21}(q) = -\left(\frac{m_2}{2} + m_3\right) a_1 a_2 C_2 - \left(\frac{m_2}{3} + m_3\right) a_2^2$$

$$M_{22}(q) = \left(\frac{m_2}{3} + m_3\right) a_2^2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
M_{31}(q) &= m_3 \\
M_{13}(q) &= M_{13}(q) = M_{23}(q) = M_{32}(q) = M_{33}(q) = 0 \\
C(q, \dot{q}) &= \begin{pmatrix} -a_1 a_2 S_2 \left[(m_2 + 2m_3) \dot{q}_1 \dot{q}_2 - \left(\frac{m_2}{2} + m_3 \right) \dot{q}_2^2 \right] \\ \left(\frac{m_2}{2} + m_3 \right) a_1 a_2 S_2 \dot{q}_1^2 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}
\end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

$$B(\dot{q}) = \begin{pmatrix} B_1(\dot{q}) \\ B_2(\dot{q}) \\ B_3(\dot{q}) \end{pmatrix} \tag{14}$$

$$G = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ -g_0 m_3 \end{pmatrix} \tag{15}$$

m_1, m_2 and m_3 are the bodies (or links) masses.

g_0 is the gravity constant.

It is worth notice that the dynamical model is obtained under some hypothesis and simplifications, such as neglecting the dry frictions and considering the links to be of parallelepiped shapes. The links are also considered to be made of homogenous materials, which is not the case in real life. These assumptions usually result in a more or less accurate model that provides data close to the experimental values of the accelerations; it involves though unavoidable modelling errors. Therefore, the robustness of the controller is of high significance for such application.

Equation (11) is of fundamental importance in the control strategy of the robot arm. In fact, a linearizing-decoupling based method will be applied on this equation in order to simplify the control process [41]. Therefore, choosing the control signal according to equation (16) will result in the system (17) which is more simple and easier to handle and control.

$$\tau = C(q, \dot{q}) + B(\dot{q}) + G + M(q)v \tag{16}$$

$$\ddot{q} = v \tag{17}$$

$v = (v_1, \dots, v_n)^T$ is the new virtual control vector, that can be computed using any convenient strategy of control, namely the Sliding Modes and the trust control techniques in this paper.

The equation (17) can be expressed with more details in (18).

$$\begin{pmatrix} \ddot{q}_1 \\ \vdots \\ \ddot{q}_n \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} v_1 \\ \vdots \\ v_n \end{pmatrix} \tag{18}$$

Each relation $\ddot{q}_k = v_k$, $k = 1, \dots, n$ from (18) can be expressed in the state space, considering the state vector $x_k^T = (x_{k1}, x_{k2})$, and the corresponding output variable $y_k = x_{k1} = q_k$ (the k^{th} joint variable) as the following:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{x}_{k1} = x_{k2} \\ \dot{x}_{k2} = v_k \end{cases} \tag{19}$$

The next step would be the definition of the references for the joint variables, thus, the motion generation.

B. Motion generation

The motion generation relies mostly on the generation of the references (or desired values) q_{kr} for the joints variables. These references can be generated using many methods including bang-bang, trapezoidal and polynomial approaches [18]. Because of the smooth moves, speeds and accelerations, the references are generated using the fifth order polynomial interpolation in this paper, as presented in (20).

$$q_{kr}(t) = q_{ki} + (q_{kf} - q_{ki})r(t) \tag{20}$$

q_{ki} and q_{kf} are the initial and the final values for the k^{th} joint position, respectively.

$r(t)$ is the fifth polynomial defined in (21).

$$r(t) = \left(\frac{10}{t_f^3} \right) t^3 - \left(\frac{15}{t_f^4} \right) t^4 + \left(\frac{6}{t_f^5} \right) t^5 \tag{21}$$

C. Control methods

The control objectives for the robot arm are for the joint variables $x_{k1} = q_k$ to follow their respective references q_{kr} . Therefore, equation (19) has to be expressed in terms of tracking errors $e_{k1} = x_{k1} - q_{kr}$ and $e_{k2} = x_{k2} - \dot{x}_{k2r}$ as the following:

$$\begin{cases} \dot{e}_{k1} = x_{k2} - \dot{q}_{kr} \\ \dot{e}_{k2} = v_k - \dot{x}_{k2r} \end{cases} \tag{22}$$

The sliding modes control

The sliding modes (SM) controller is a robust controller that has been used so far successfully in multiple applications [42], [5], [43], [6], [44], [45]. The main well known inconvenience of this controller, is the shattering phenomenon that is problematic for control systems, but more specifically for mechanical structures such as robotic arms. In fact, the shattering phenomenon means brutal changes and fast variations of the speeds and applied forces/torques, which results in vibrations, thus fast damages and short lifetime of the robotic arm mechanical structure. Therefore, several variants of the SM controller have been introduced, such as the twisting and the super-twisting algorithms, in order to smooth and reduce the shattering effects. Nevertheless, these variants are PID controller equivalent robust versions, thus a slowness of the response is expected due to the integration components, which reduces consequently the precision of the controlled system response [46].

For a given system defined by the state equations (22), a sliding modes based Back-stepping methodology is applied. This method is inspired by the approach presented in [47]. Because the state equations (22) corresponds to a second order system, the Back-stepping methodology implies two steps to be followed for this specific application [48], [49], [50], in order to determine the control signals' expressions:

Step 1: control x_{k1} using x_{k2}

The aim of this step is to define a reference for x_{k2} . In order to find the expression of x_{k2} , a Lyapunov function $V_1 = \frac{1}{2} e_{k1}^2$

is considered. The time derivative of V_1 will result in $\dot{V}_1 = e_{k1}\dot{e}_{k1}$. The product $V_1\dot{V}_1$ has to be negative in order to guarantee x_{k1} to track its reference q_{1r} . Therefore, the following expression (23) for x_{k2} is obtained. This expression actually represents the reference for x_{k2} to be followed. This leads to the second step.

$$x_{k2r} = \dot{q}_{kr} - K_1(x_{k1} - q_{kr}) \quad (23)$$

K_1 is a positive constant.

Step 2 : control x_{k2} using v_k

In order to find the expression of the control signal v_k , a second Lyapunov function $V_2 = V_1 + S_k$ is considered.

$S_k = \frac{1}{2}e_{k2}^2$ is the sliding surface defined for the k^{th} joint variable control problem. This surface ensures the invariance condition: $S_k = 0 \Rightarrow x_{k1} \rightarrow q_{kr}$.

Proof.

$S_k = 0$ implies $x_{k2} \rightarrow x_{k2r}$. This means that: $\dot{e}_{k1} \rightarrow -K_1(x_{k1} - q_{kr})$. Therefore, the product $e_{k1}\dot{e}_{k1}$ is definite negative and ensures the convergence $x_{k1} \rightarrow q_{kr}$, thus the achievement of the control objectives for the joint variable q_k .

The time derivative of V_2 will result in $\dot{V}_2 = e_{k1}\dot{e}_{k1} + e_{k2}\dot{e}_{k2}$. The product $V_2\dot{V}_2$ has to be negative in order to guarantee x_{k2} to track its reference x_{k2r} . Therefore, the following expression (24) is obtained for the control signal v_k .

$$v_k = \ddot{q}_{kr} + K_1(x_{k2} - \dot{q}_{kr}) - K_2 \text{sign}[x_{k2} - \dot{q}_{kr} + K_1(x_{k1} - q_{kr})] \quad (24)$$

This control signal expression has been chosen in order to ensure the condition of attraction.

Proof.

If the control variable expression v_k that has been obtained in (24) is inserted in $\dot{e}_{k2} = v_k - \dot{x}_{k2r}$ from (22), this will give the following expression for \dot{e}_{k2}

$$\dot{e}_{k2} = \ddot{q}_{kr} + K_1(x_{k2} - \dot{q}_{kr}) - K_2 \text{sign}[x_{k2} - \dot{q}_{kr} + K_1(x_{k1} - q_{kr})] - \dot{x}_{k2r} \quad (25)$$

Moreover, replacing \dot{x}_{k2r} in (25) by its corresponding expression (26) that can be derived from (23), will lead to the expression (27)

$$\dot{x}_{k2r} = \ddot{q}_{kr} - K_1(\dot{x}_{k1} - \dot{q}_{kr}) \quad (26)$$

$$\dot{e}_{k2} = -K_2 \text{sign}[x_{k2} - \dot{q}_{kr} + K_1(x_{k1} - q_{kr})] \quad (27)$$

From (27), it is clear that \dot{S}_k is definite negative. Therefore, the attraction condition $S_k\dot{S}_k \leq 0$ of the Sliding Modes controller (24) is validated.

Step 1 and step 2 will be applied for each joint variable q_k of the robot arm, and will result in the corresponding control signal expression v_k as presented in (24).

Belief theory concepts and definitions

Introducing the Dempster-Shafer (D-S) theory [51], [52], [53], also known as the belief theory or the theory of evidence, implies some concepts and definitions, including the following.

A frame of discernment Θ is the set of all possible propositions or information that can be considered about a given problem. These propositions are exclusive and independent. The power set 2^Θ includes all the possible subsets of Θ , including the empty set ϕ and the frame of discernment Θ itself.

In the theory of evidence, a mass m is assigned to each subset of the power set 2^Θ [54]. A mass m has a value between 0 and 1. This defines the mass function (28). The mass function verifies the two axioms (29) and (30).

$$m: 2^\Theta \rightarrow [0,1] \quad (28)$$

$$m(\phi) = 0 \quad (29)$$

$$\sum_{A \subseteq \Theta} m(A) = 1 \quad (30)$$

The belief function $Bel(\cdot)$ for a proposition A is defined by (31). It sets the belief committed to A .

$$Bel(A) = \sum_{B \subseteq A} m(B) \quad (31)$$

The belief theory also offers the possibility to handle the combinations between multiple independent sources of information using the Dempster's rule of combination that will compute the resulting mass function.

Using two information sources S_1 and S_2 for instance, will define the corresponding mass functions m_1 and m_2 . Therefore, the Dempster's rule of combination is defined using the orthogonal addition \oplus as defined in (32) [55], [56].

$$m(A) = m_1(A) \oplus m_2(A) = \frac{1}{1-\eta} \sum m_1(A_i) m_2(A_j)$$

$$\text{Where } A_i, A_j \subseteq \Theta, A_i \cap A_j = A$$

$$\eta = \sum_{A_i \cap A_j \neq \phi} m_1(A_i) m_2(A_j) \quad (32)$$

Depending on the trust allocated to the source of information, it is possible to strengthen or weaken the mass of each source using a weight $w_i \in [0,1]$ associated to the source S_i [57], such as

$$w_i = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{The source } S_i \text{ is not reliable at all} \\ 1 & \text{The source } S_i \text{ is completely reliable} \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

The new mass function will result in (34).

$$m_{si} = w_i m_i(A), \forall A \neq \Theta \quad (34)$$

The trust control

The trust control technique is inspired by the previous belief theory concepts and definitions. It considers the question of interest: What is the best control signal value to

be applied to the system in order to achieve the control objectives? [15]

In order to answer this question, two sources of information are considered: (i) S_1 : the measured value (provided by the sensor) and (ii) S_2 : the estimated value (provided by the model).

The trust controller will evaluate the amount of trust allocated to a set of possible values with regard to the information on the output provided by the sensor and the one provided by the model. Each information is trusted with a degree of reliability defined by its allocated weight.

The number of possible values for the control variable is infinite. Therefore, a finite set of singletons v_{k1}, \dots, v_{kl} is considered for the k^{th} control variable v_k .

For the decision making, the normalized errors e_{N1} and e_{N2} are computed in (35) for each singleton.

$$\begin{cases} e_{N1} = \frac{x_{mes} - x_r}{\max(x_{mes} - x_r)} \\ e_{N2} = \frac{x_{mod} - x_r}{\max(x_{mod} - x_r)} \end{cases} \quad (35)$$

x_{mes} is the measured value of x

x_{mod} is the estimated value of x using a model

The next step would be to determine the mass functions or distributions properly, so they verify the two axioms (29) and (30). In order to do so, it is essential to consider a mass function that takes into account the modeling and measurement errors on the output of the system on one hand. On the other hand, it appears significant that the mass function should increase with the error decreasing and vice versa. The later statement is logic, since whenever the error is high, the corresponding control signal value is not reliable and vice versa. The expressions in (36) are therefore derived from this specific reasoning.

$$\begin{cases} m_{e1} = 1 - |e_{N1}| \\ m_{e2} = 1 - |e_{N2}| \end{cases} \quad (36)$$

The only element left is to make sure that the axioms (29) and (30) are verified. In fact, it is assumed that leaving the system to itself, without a control signal will result in the system diverging towards the maximum error and not achieving its control objectives. Therefore, the corresponding mass will converge to 0. On the other hand, according to the Taylor series of the exponential function (37) the expressions m_{e1} and m_{e2} will both converge to 0 for small normalized errors.

$$e^{-|x|} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-|e|)^n}{n!} \approx 1 - |e| + \mathcal{O}(|e|^2) \quad (37)$$

Therefore, the considered mass functions associated to the two sources of information S_1 and S_2 are presented in (38).

$$\begin{cases} m_{s1} = w_1 (1 - |e_{N1}|) \\ m_{s2} = \frac{w_2}{l} (1 - |e_{N2}|) \end{cases} \quad (38)$$

w_1 and w_2 are weights to be introduced in order to enable the user to increase or decrease the trust allocated to the

measurement data rather than to the model's data, and inversely.

Consequently, the selected control signal value, from the set v_{k1}, \dots, v_{kl} , that will be applied is the value that provides the highest belief or involves the highest trust after combining the information of the two sources using the Dempster operator.

The following algorithm displays the computation of the trust control at a given time t :

Define the reference: x_{kr} ;

Acquire the system output: x_{mes} ;

Compute the normalized error : $e_{N1} = \frac{x_{mes} - x_r}{\max(x_{mes} - x_r)}$;

Compute the weighted mass distribution:

$$m_{s1} = w_1 (1 - |e_{N1}|);$$

For $i = 0, \dots, l$

 Compute the model output: x_{mod} ;

 Compute the normalized error: $e_{N2} = \frac{x_{mod} - x_r}{\max(x_{mod} - x_r)}$;

 Compute the weighted mass distribution:

$$m_{s2i} = \frac{w_2}{l} (1 - |e_{N2}|);$$

 Compute the combined distribution mass:

$$m_i = m_{s1} \oplus m_{s2i}(A)$$

End

Find the highest m_i and apply the corresponding control value v_{ki} to the system.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For the simulations, a SCARA robotic arm was considered with the parameters given in Table II [16].

TABLE II
THE PARAMETERS OF THE SCARA ROBOTIC ARM USED FOR THE SIMULATION

Link	$a_k(m)$	$\alpha_k(rad)$	$d_k(m)$	$\theta_k(rad)$
1	0.2	π	0.5	q_1
2	0.2	0	0	q_2
3	0	0	q_3	

The references for the joints variables were generated using the fifth order polynomial interpolation defined in (20) and (21), considering the initial time $t_0 = 0s$ and the final time $t_f = 2s$, as well as the following initial and final values for each joint variable : $q_{1i} = \frac{\pi}{4}$, $q_{1f} = \frac{\pi}{3}$, $q_{2i} = \frac{\pi}{6}$, $q_{2f} = \frac{\pi}{2}$, $q_{3i} = 0.2$, $q_{3f} = 0.3$.

The following values of the gains are used for the Sliding Modes controller: $K_1 = 3$ and $K_2 = 0.5$.

As for the trust controller, a cloud of values for the control signals were considered between -1 and +1, with a set point of 0.1. The weights were allocated as the following: $w_1 = 0.7$ and $w_2 = 0.5$. This means that it has been chosen to trust the data from the sensors (the measurements: data coming from the first source of information S_1) more than the data of the models (the model outputs: coming from the second source of

information S_2).

For the simulation, a 10% additive modeling error have been introduced on both model and measurements in order to evaluate the robustness of the controllers with regard to such errors.

Simulation results

Figures 2, 4, 6 and 8 present the simulation results for the joint variables, the tracking errors, the control variables as well as the control energies related to the Sliding Modes controller, while Figures 3, 5, 7 and 9 illustrate the simulation results for the joint variables, the tracking errors, the control variables as well as the control energies obtained using the trust control technique.

Fig. 2. The joint variables using the Sliding Modes controller

Fig. 3. Joint variables using the trust control

Fig. 4. The tracking errors using the Sliding Modes control

Fig. 5. Tracking errors using the trust control

Fig. 6. The Sliding Modes control signals

Fig. 7. The trust control signals

Fig. 8. The energy consumed by the Sliding Modes controller

Fig. 9. The energy consumed by the trust controller

Discussion

It can be observed that both Sliding Modes and trust controllers have robust results with regards to measurements and modelling errors as illustrated in Figures 2 and 3. It can be clearly noticed that the each joint variable is following its reference. However, the tracking errors curves, illustrated in Figures 4 and 5, show better performances of the trust controller at the final value of the joint variables when it comes to precision. The results also highlight less fluctuations of the output, which could not be directly seen from the outputs curves yet clearly visible in the errors results. It is

important to underline the fact that less fluctuations on the outputs has many benefits on the mechanical structure as it improves its lifetime on one hand. On the other hand, this provides more precise trajectory tracking, especially for applications that require high precision like surgical tasks. Moreover, the trust controller signal presents less shattering and brutal changes for similar operating condition under the Sliding Modes control as shown by the results presented in Figures 6 and 7. This is due to the fact that the Sliding Modes controller uses the system output directly to apply higher control values to overcome the errors, while the trust controller relies on the trust allocated to the data in order to make the decision of the control to be applied to the system.

Finally, it can be noticed that the trust controller achieved similar or better performances than the Sliding Modes controller using about 30% less energy for similar operating conditions, as it can be appreciated in Figures 8 and 9.

IV. CONCLUSION

This work provides a comparative study of performances between two robust controllers, namely the Sliding Modes and the trust controllers in order to solve a trajectory tracking problem for a robotic arm. The former controller relies on the sign of the error in order to apply a sufficiently high control signal to overcome the errors, while the later relies on the trust allocated to the data in order to make the decision on the most trustworthy control value to be applied to the system. The results presented in this paper underlined almost similar performances with regard to the precision of the system. However, the trust controller presented less fluctuations for the outputs and a more energy efficient control signals for similar operating conditions compared to the Sliding Modes controller.

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